

Minutes of the 62nd Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 31st January 2019

(This document was finalised on 18th June 2019)

Present:

(BB) Dr Barbara Brooks^{1,7}
(CJW) Dr Chris Walden^{3,4,6}
(DAH) Dr David Hooper^{4,5,6} Secretary
(DK) Dr Dirk Klugmann⁶
(GV) Prof Geraint Vaughan^{4,8} Chair
(GAP) Dr Graham Parton^{2,4,6}
(HC) Dr Helen Clark
(HMAR) Dr Hugo Ricketts^{4,8}
(LD) Mr Les Dean⁵

Affiliation:

¹ (AMF) Atmospheric Measurement Facility
² (CEDA) Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
³ (CFARR) Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research
⁴ (NCAS) National Centre for Atmospheric Science
⁵ NERC MST Radar Facility
⁶ (RAL) Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
⁷ University of Leeds
⁸ University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
EGN Emily Norton
ESA European Space Agency
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NAWDEX North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
UTC Universal Time
VAT Value Added Tax

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 61st meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made no progress on action item 47.2.1. However, he acknowledged its im-

portance in view of the fact that the existing data processing PC (Claudius) is very old and must be replaced. GAP suggested that it would be good to shift over from Python version 2 to version 3 at the same time. The later will soon be available on the jasmin platform.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

DISCONTINUED

DAH suggested that action item 47.3.2 should be discontinued since it will be dealt with by an overarching need to release the backlog of cloud base data and to release the backscatter power data. The latter have never been made publicly available. DAH finds them very useful for checking that the tipping bucket rain gauge is working correctly.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data available through CEDA in NCAS-approved files.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH reported that action item 51.4.1 was ongoing and that he would give more details in section 4b.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that no progress has been made on action item 51.4.2. There was a brief discussion as to whether MST radar wind profile data should continue to be sent to the EUCOS (EUMETNET Composite Observing System) E-PROFILE programme after the Met Office's contract comes to an end in April 2019. However, further discussion was delayed until section 4g.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.1 DAH to consult with members of the data user community in order to establish the sort of instrument performance details that would be useful.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that he had discussed action item 58.1.1 with Chris Lee, whose requirements had led to it. Chris wants to be able to determine how many MST Radar transmitters are in operation at any one time since this affects the radar beam pattern and so could affect the values of spectral width. BB suggested that such details might be put in the "comments" global attribute of netCDF files. DAH pointed out that this information is often determined from beam steering unit messages, which are sent by e-mail, and so it is not easy to access it at file creation time. GV suggested that although it would be best to store this information in the metadata for each data products file, it would be useful to make it available in the short term as a time series (perhaps at hourly intervals) in an additional file.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 59.3.1 DAH to arrange for the clearance of willow saplings from the MST radar's antenna array as soon as possible.

ONGOING

DAH reported that action item 59.3.1 is ongoing. He will give an update in section 3d.

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the version 4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which version 3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not yet started on action item 60.2.1. However, if anyone requires v4 files for a date that is not yet available, he can create them on request. GV stated that he was concerned that this job would not get done unless there was a plan for it. He added that there also needs to be a plan for creating version 4 files for dates when no version 3 files are available. He noted that the quality of the version 4 data was noticeably better than that of previous versions of MST radar data products.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a mechanism for releasing files containing small amounts of suspect data to the CEDA archives and of labelling them in such a way that their suspect status is obvious.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that action item 61.3.1 had been completed and that he would give further details in section 3a.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

DAH reported that he and GAP had implemented a mechanism for releasing MST radar files containing suspect data into the CEDA archives, i.e. addressing action item 61.3.1. The fact that the file has failed a visual quality control check is recorded in the file's "history" global attribute, details of the problem and of the affected time-altitude region are added to the "comment" global attribute, and the word "suspect" is added to the file name. HC was interested to know whether other details, such as the existence of mountain waves, could be added to the file's metadata. DAH responded that he had no plans to do this, although he did note down details of interest when he scrutinised the quick-look plots as part of his final quality control checks. GAP clarified that the procedure described above was an interim solution until DAH had time to release updated files in which the affected areas were flagged as containing unreliable data. BB pointed out that the flagging system defined by the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) data standards should be adopted. She added that the prefix "nerc" in data file names was gradually being dropped in favour of "ncas". GV pointed out that long term measurement programs will not technically be covered by the new Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF). The latter, which will come into being in April 2020, is a merger between the existing Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) and NERC Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (NFARR), which itself is a recent merger between the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR) and the MSTRF.

GAP reported that the presentation of the CEDA catalogue pages has been improved. Implementation of the "elastic search" technique in the near future will allow search results to be returned much more quickly than is currently possible. He warned users of the jasmin system that Tuesday mornings should

be considered an at risk period in case of site maintenance. Finally, he reported that CEDA have been thinking of reclassifying quick-look plots as a data product. At present, they only have auxiliary status and so are not preserved in the same way as data files. GV reported that he was not able to easily find v4 MST radar data files and wondered if this was to do with different file naming conventions.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

NEW

3b) Electricity - DAH

In order for the local distribution company to be able to carry out maintenance on their equipment, the electricity supply for the whole of the Capel Dewi area was unavailable between 09:00 and 16:15 UTC on 8th November 2018. Another scheduled outage occurred between 09:10 and 14:20 UTC on 14th December 2018. In both of these cases, all of the equipment at the radar site had to be powered down.

The Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) units indicated that brief (~1 s) disruptions to the input occurred on five occasions: three times on 5th September 2018, at 10:46 UTC on 25th September, and at 10:22 UTC on 29th October. Four disruptions of varying durations - one 6 s long - occurred on 28th November 2018. A 5 s disruption occurred on 27th January 2019. There was an unscheduled 80 minute outage (between 16:42 and 18:06 UTC) on Sunday 27th January 2019. This last one caused all of the instruments to shut down. DAH was able to restart the MST Radar remotely. However, the Windows PC “*gaius*”, which logs Campbell Scientific logger and LD40 data, did not automatically restart when the power was restored and had to be booted manually on the following day.

3c) Telecommunications

The speed of the broadband link to the site became extremely slow during the afternoon of 21st September 2018. The service provider could see no cause for the problem but performed a remote reset at the local exchange for good measure. This, and LD changing the phone/broadband filter, had no effect. Normal service was resumed when the router was power-cycled on the following day. DAH commented on the fact that this was the first time he could remember the Draytek router needing to be rebooted. It has proved to be so reliable that the GSM-Auto switch, which allows it to be power-cycled upon receipt of a text message, is no longer connected to its power-supply.

3d) Miscellaneous

GV reported that the license for the Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler (BLWP) had been renewed in November 2018. The application form changes every year and so it is always time-consuming to complete. BB asked whether a similar license was needed for the Met Office's BLWP at Chilbolton. DAH reported that he had completely forgotten about renewing the five-yearly MST radar license. However, when he contacted Ofcom, he was surprised to hear that it had been renewed by a member of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) Security staff. He suspected that they thought it covered their walkie-talkies. The new license is valid until 31st May 2023.

DAH noted that the MSTRF's electricity bills have increased by approximately 20% since April 2018. This is because UKRI (UK Research and Innovation), the body that has taken over combined legal responsibility for all of the research councils, does not have charitable status. Consequently NERC facilities are now liable for 20% rather than 5% VAT (Value Added Tax) on their electricity bills and must also pay a climate change levy.

DAH reported that he had held a meeting with members of RAL's Estates team at the beginning of January 2019 to discuss clearance of willows from the MST Radar antenna array, i.e. regarding action item 59.3.1. Representatives of one of the facilities management contractors (Vinci) used by RAL were also present at the meeting. They have identified one of their own sub-contractors who is willing to carry out

the work as soon as an order can be placed with them. DAH must first set up a mechanism to access the money that was awarded by NERC to the MSTRF for carrying out estates work. It is currently being held by NCAS at the University of Leeds. DAH reported that he had also asked the contractor to look at other estates issues associated with the radar site. GV agreed that it would be good to look at cutting back the trees that are starting to overhang the lidar installation. LD suggested that clearance of the antenna array's drainage system might be something else that could be looked at.

DAH is in the process of arranging for the installation of the "new" MST Radar transmitters. These were purchased in March 2016, but the MSTRF lacked sufficient funds at that time to have them installed. NCAS has recently awarded the MSTRF money to cover this job. DAH is waiting to hear whether NCAS can place the order for the work directly. This would avoid having to pay 20% VAT by first transferring the money to RAL. DAH noted that one or two additional members of Chilbolton group staff would likely be required to help with the removal of the existing transmitters and possibly with some of the installation work. He noted that the existing cables feeding the 5 sectors of the antenna array were not very flexible. He wondered whether it would be possible to bring them closer together to attach to the outputs of the new system. He made a note to raise this issue with the suppliers.

BB indicated that data files from the new radar systems must be compliant with NCAS's data standards before they can be deposited in the CEDA archive. GV expressed his hope that the new transmitters would make the radar more reliable. He emphasised the longer-term need for equipment at the radar site to be capable of being operated unattended for as long as possible. He stressed that arranging for the willow tree clearance and for the transmitter installation should be DAH's top priorities over the next 6 months.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to manage the installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton group staff, for the latter part of 2019.

NEW

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

DAH reported that he planned to make publicly available the python software that he has recently created for accessing the MSTRF's NASA Ames data files. It is currently restricted to the one dimensional datasets, e.g. for LD40 cloud base data, Campbell Scientific surface met data, and Campbell Scientific surface wind data.

DAH is in the process of establishing the characteristics of the surface met and wind measurements made by the different sensors. This has grown out of GAP's request for him to produce a quality statement for the Vaisala WXT510 instrument. He (DAH) has noticed that the temperature (and humidity) measurements made by the Campbell Scientific data logger and the Vaisala WXT510 are closely matched under overcast conditions, but can differ by over 1°C (several percent) under clear sky conditions - e.g. compare data for the 2nd and 19th July 2013. The temperatures measured by the Campbell Scientific sensor exceed those measured by the WXT510 until late in the afternoon, when the pattern is reversed. DAH wondered whether this was a result of the Campbell Scientific sensor receiving more reflected sunlight from the northern side of the valley. He showed that the Campbell Scientific logger detects noticeably stronger downwelling shortwave flux during the afternoon than during the morning around mid-summer (see e.g. data for 22nd June 2014). Moreover, using Sky-Camera images he has found that a sharp reduction in the flux during the late afternoon is not caused the Sun becoming partially obscured by the landscape. This does not happen until much later in the evening. BB suggested that the difference in temperatures might instead be a consequence of both sensors being housed within un aspirated shields. She pointed out that the lack of aspiration can be particularly noticeable under conditions of slow wind speeds. She asked whether one of the sensors could be moved closer to the other one so that colocated

measurements could be compared. The sensors are currently located approximately 50 m apart.

BB suggested that data from the Campbell Scientific data loggers should be made available in files that conform to NCAS data standards. GV noted that the data are used by a wide range of people outside of the atmospheric science community who might have difficulties dealing with netCDF files. He suggested that the user community should therefore be consulted before any changes are made. GAP noted that the OPeNDAP server provides an option for outputting data from netCDF files in text-based format. BB suggested that maybe both the NASA Ames files and corresponding netCDF files should be made available simultaneously. GAP confirmed that this was a possibility from a CEDA perspective.

ACTION ITEM 62.4.1 DAH to provide BB with a list of all of the instruments operated by the MSTRF and of all of the data products available. DAH should provide as much detail as possible.

NEW

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH reported that there had been no issues with these sensors over the past six months.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

In the context of action item 51.4.1, DAH reported that CFARR also had a requirement to replace some of its data loggers. Consequently, DAH has been working together with two members of CFARR staff in order to collectively evaluate the capabilities of a Campbell Scientific CR1000X data logger. The 3G communications issues have now been sorted out, allowing the loggers for both the CFARR and MSTRF sites to directly upload their raw data to the same computer.

BB pointed out that she uses Raspberry Pis for many data logging applications, including one at the top of Ben Nevis. These can fulfil many of the same functions as Campbell Scientific data loggers and are considerably cheaper. She recommended using a unidirectional antenna if the 3G reception at Frongoch proved to be a problem (DAH had found that the signal strength varied considerably over short distances when he had visited the site 6 months previously). She recommended that Campbell Scientific data loggers should be calibrated on a yearly basis.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH has been working on software to create netCDF files from the raw data captured from the WXT520. Since the WXT instruments only produce precipitation messages (at 10 s intervals) during a precipitation event, he has been considering on how best to add padding values in order to make the data easier to interpret. Clearly it will be necessary to insert missing datum values at the start and end of periods when no data were captured (this can be determined from gaps in the PTU and wind data, which are captured at regular 60 s intervals) in order to distinguish these from periods of no precipitation. However, he is also considering whether it is useful to add samples indicating zero rain rates immediately before and after a precipitation event. BB reported that Vaisala have discontinued the WXT520 instrument and replaced it with a WXT530.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH reported that he had most of the software in place to be able to create netCDF files of LD40 data. However, he was waiting for feedback from BB on how best to record the backscatter data. These are given as binned values of the natural logarithm of the range-squared-corrected backscatter power. GV commented that the backscatter coefficient is what is really required. However, the LD40 was not designed to be able to deliver this. He added that he had capital money available to buy a Luft ceilometer for the Capel Dewi site, but had been waiting for the new depolarisation model to become available. BB pointed out that there were no other LD40s being operated within NCAS.

ACTION ITEM 62.4.2 DAH to send BB details of raw LD40 data products so that the most appropriate way of storing them in netCDF files can be agreed.

NEW

4e) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that he was leading the process of defining a metadata standard for use with NCAS images. He had given a presentation on this at a recent NCAS data project meeting. Images from Sky-Camera-2 and the NLC camera will be released once the new standard has been agreed upon and applied to the images.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH drew attention to the “weather news” section of the August 2018 issue of the Royal Met Soc’s Weather publication - <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/wea.3136>. It features a plot of Mesosphere Summer Echoes (MSEs) observed by the MST Radar in a short article about unusually frequent and extensive displays of NLC seen from northern Europe during the final week of June 2018.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics for the past six months, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpett of the Met Office. The number of observations reported daily has remained quasi-constant over the past 6 months, with large reductions seen on only a few days. The EUCOS (EU-METNET Composite Observing System) root mean square wind vector difference values have mostly been within the 5 m s^{-1} target. “Availability” and “Timeliness” values have comfortably remained within their target values. Met Office model-comparison statistics also show acceptable data quality over the past 6 months.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. The transmitters have been relatively reliable over the past six months. LD swapped beam steering unit 90 on 25th September 2018 after it began giving intermittent indications of a low supply voltage on the previous day. He changed it again on 15th January 2019 after it showed elevated Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) values. The fuse for transmitter TXB only blew on 3 occasions - on 7th September 2018, on 23rd October 2018, and on 24th October 2018 - and that for TXC on one occasion: on 25th August 2018. Only two days were identified as containing suspect data: 3rd August 2018, between 10:25 and 11:05 UTC at just above 11 km, and 23rd October 2018, between 10:10 and 11:20 UTC at around 16 km.

DAH reported that the Met Office had finally decided to discontinue its long-running commercial contract for being supplied with near-real-time MST Radar wind-profile data from April 2019. In recent years this has contributed 25% of the MSTRF’s operating costs and so the loss will have a large impact. After a discussion, it was agreed that the MSTRF should continue to send the wind-profile data to the E-PROFILE programme since the data are also being operationally assimilated by a number of other European met services. GAP noted that he had contacts within E-PROFILE and that the programme now took data from other types of atmospheric profiling instruments including laser ceilometers. CJW wondered whether the CFARR ceilometers should submit to this network.

5. Guest Instrument Report

GV and HMAR gave a report on their equipment. The ozone lidar is currently working, but at such low output power that it is effectively out of action. LD added that it had frozen up over a weekend in late January 2019 and that it had taken quite a lot of effort to thaw it out. GV reported that the output power was also low on the other lidar. The hope was to operate both lidars together so that the depolarisation ratio could be inferred. However, there had not been much clear weather recently to allow any operations. BB pointed out that according to the AMF booking system, the lidar was available for booking. She asked for the calendar to be kept up to date.

The BLWP is currently in operation at Capel Dewi. However, there have been problems with the computer crashing, which has led to loss of data. It seemed to work okay with a cloned hard drive. The main problem is that the automatic change in sampling interval, which adapts to the fastest measured wind speed, often fails to avoid velocity aliasing of spectral data. Although it is possible to correct for this, it would be better if it did not happen in the first place. DK pointed out that the Met Office had disabled this feature on their own BLWPs. GV reported that this functionality was necessary in order to improve velocity resolution under conditions of low wind speeds. He has found that the level of ground clutter has reduced since the trees growing on the south side of the Capel Dewi valley were cut down. However, there is still an occasional problem with clutter from a wind turbine, which is located approximately 3 km away.

BB asked for details of the BLWP's availability to also be included in the AMF booking calendar since she had assumed that the instrument was still in operation at Cardington. Moreover, according to the latest data plots, the BLWP appears to still be in Portugal. She advised Emily Norton (EGN) to report this to Dan and James at NCAS. She wondered whether fitting a GPS receiver to the profiler could help to keep track of its location. GV pointed out that it was still necessary to manually input the location details into the software. GAP pointed out that when the BLWP was in operation at Davidstow (Cornwall), its stated coordinates put it somewhere in the English Channel.

DK was interested to know the science questions that the lidar operations were designed to address. GV explained that aerosol transport was the primary subject of interest. DK wondered whether it would therefore be useful to have another lidar at Chilbolton. CJW clarified that one was due to be installed at the site in the nearish future. GV finished off by saying that his "home-made" lidar was due for a redesign. It was made as a proof of concept. However, it was neither transportable nor calibrated.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Red Sun event over the UK on 16th October 2017 - HMAR

The reason for the Sun appearing red and the sky appearing yellow was the presence of atmospheric aerosols with a high optical depth. The question is whether dust from the Sahara or smoke particles from forest fires in Portugal were responsible. The MSG satellite image for 12:00 UTC on 16th October shows a band of aerosol over England, but not over Wales. The synoptic pressure chart shows that this air was drawn up from the south by the presence of ex-hurricane Ophelia to the south-west of the British Isles. Data were analysed from lidars operated by the Met Office and by the UK lidar community at Capel Dewi, Brighton, Chilbolton, and Bayfordbury. These show that the aerosols were seen earliest in the west of southern Britain and only later towards the east. Moreover, the duration of the layer was only 2 hours in the west, but 6-8 hours in SE England. Finally, the altitude of the base of the layer increased over time. Back trajectories suggest that Portugal and the Sahara could both be source regions for the air found over Aberystwyth. A lidar in Portugal saw an aerosol layer, but with much lower concentrations than seen over the British Isles. One of the forward trajectories from Portugal passes over Aberystwyth.

The lidar backscatter was highly depolarised, which initially suggested forest fire smoke as the source. However, any smoke would be 8 hours old by the time it passed over the British Isles and so could have coagulated into complex shapes. DK drew attention to a region of backscatter observed by both cloud radar and lidar, which occurs above a region observed just by lidar. GV pointed out that that is why vertical velocity information is needed. This region could be populated by loose agglomerations with low density, as opposed to large particles.

HMAR has also looked at observations made by a GRIMM optical particle counter. However, he is not quite sure about the interpretation of the data. BB suggested that he show the concentrations as a function of (log of) particle diameter rather than of size bin number. She warned that with the particles being

concentrated in only 1 or 2 size bins he would not be able to differentiate between Poisson and Gaussian distributions. She also warned that the instrument is calibrated using spherical particles, whereas the particles of interest might not be spherical.

HMAR would like to extend his analysis by considering data from the Chilbolton-based wind-profiler (for which he will need EGN's help) and from Mace Head. BB also recommended that he looked at the Weyborne datasets.

6b) Low inertial stability - GV

This presentation arises from work that GV has been undertaking with David Schultz using data from the NAWDEX (North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment) campaign period. The aim is to see if the presence of inertial instability - indicated by Potential Vorticity values of less than 0.2 PVU on GFS 320 K charts - leads to effects that can be observed by the MST Radar, e.g. inertia-gravity waves or turbulence. Since the causes of turbulence are diverse, other mechanisms must be ruled out before inertial stability can be considered. The Manucast model was found to be unstable for some of the days being analysed. In one case it appears to generate mountain waves, but not exclusively in in the regions where they would be expected to be found. GV was surprised to find 7 examples of inertial instability during the 1 month of the NAWDEX campaign period. Anticyclonic flow appears to be an important contributory factor. Although this analysis began primarily as an activity to support a grant proposal, it turned out to be very illuminating. He thought that the MST Radar was clearly the most appropriate instrument for such a study.

6c) Updates on DK's projects - DK

DK's development of a cloud radar remains a side project. He has received money to develop the hardware for the system and he hopes to have a functional unit by the summer. It will first be deployed to Heathrow, but he hopes that it could be operated at the MST radar site at some point in the future.

Since Honeywell Aerospace have a presence on the Harwell campus, DK has received cross cutting funding to work with them on his ship-based wind-profiler idea. DK will work on the back end whilst Honeywell will provide a power amplifier. A 300 W unit is available for continuous wave applications. The initial system will only point towards the vertical. When it is operated at sea, the movement of the ship will lead to variations in the beam pointing direction. A method still needs to be developed to combine the information from the resulting spread in pointing directions.

BB asked whether the cloud radar observations had been compared with those made by the Kepler (35 GHz) system. DK responded that the current system is only able to detect precipitation and so it has been operated alongside Copernicus (also 35 GHz) rather than Kepler. BB also suggested that it might be useful to operate Kepler at the MST radar site. CJW agreed, but pointed out that there is high demand for Kepler. BB drew attention to the fact that NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) operates a ship-based wind-profiling system in the US.

7. Any Other Business

The subject of the Met Office discontinuing the contract for the supply for MST radar wind profile was discussed in further detail. It was agreed that data should continue to be sent to E-PROFILE for the benefit of the other met agencies who are operationally assimilating them. CJW pointed out that DAH would need to find a way of covering the 15% shortfall in his funding. He wondered whether there was any potential in validation of data from the new European Space Agency (ESA) Aeolus satellite mission. GV agreed that this would be a good thing for the MSTRF to be involved with, but noted that it would be very difficult to obtain UK national capability funding to cover such work. DK suggested looking into ESA funding for integrated applications, e.g. by combining satellite and ground-based observations.

ACTION ITEM 62.7.1 DAH to contact EUCOS, before the end of March 2019, to arrange for near-real-time MST radar wind-profile to continue to be delivered to the E-PROFILE programme.

NEW

The date of the next meeting was provisionally set for late June 2019 with a suggestion that 20th June would be a good date.